

Exploring the Environmental Effects of Urbanization in Monrovia

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Abstract:

Monrovia, the capital city of Liberia, is undergoing rapid urbanization, leading to significant ecological and environmental challenges. This study aims to investigate the temporal and spatial changes in urbanization and their impact on the ecological environment in Monrovia from 2015 to 2023. Utilizing Landsat satellite images, OpenStreetMap data, and AQICN atmospheric particulate data (PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀). We analyzed urban patterns, building dynamics, traffic networks, and population growth. Our methodological approach involved spatial analysis and temporal

comparisons to assess land use changes and their ecological consequences. Our findings indicate substantial land use changes, with a notable increase in residential areas at the expense of natural and agricultural lands, resulting in habitat fragmentation and biodiversity loss. Economic growth in the central business district has exacerbated ecological degradation, while expanded road networks have increased surface runoff and habitat fragmentation. Air quality analysis shows rising levels of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀, posing significant health risks to residents. Additionally, the reduction in water bodies and forest cover has degraded water quality and heightened flood risks. This study underscores the urgent need for sustainable urban planning practices, including the adoption of renewable energy sources, emission control technologies, and enhanced air quality monitoring. Furthermore, community-based approaches and citizen science activities are essential for engaging local residents in pollution monitoring and advocacy, fostering partnerships for the sustainable development of Monrovia. Our research highlights the critical need for integrated strategies to mitigate the adverse effects of urbanization on the environment and public health.

Keywords: *Urbanization, Ecological impact, Monrovia, Land Use, Air Quality.*

Introduction

Urbanization, as described by Kingsley Davis, involves the transfer of people from rural to urban areas (Islam, 2024) or a shift in the proportion of the overall population residing in urban areas (Zerbo, 2022). This process is characterized by growing urban areas and increasing urban populations, strongly related with industrialization, modernization, and rationalization. It can refer to a specific situation at a given moment or the progressive increase of the urban population over time, signifying a historic and fast change in human social roots internationally. Liberia typifies this pattern, reflecting global trends with substantial influence on its growth trajectory. Understanding the complexity of urbanization in Liberia is vital for tackling the myriad issues and opportunities that occur as its cities grow, influencing citizens' lives and societal structure (Hu et al., 2023).

An ecosystem is a complex unit of living creatures inside a defined area, including their physical surrounds and interactions. It encompasses abiotic components including minerals, soil, water, and sunlight, and biotic components encompassing all living organisms. The energy flow and nutrient cycling connect these components together, generating unique ecosystems that range from tiny water drops to enormous landscapes. Ecosystem health, a phrase used in environmental research and management since the 1980s (O'Brien, Townsend, Hale, Sharley, & Pettigrove, 2016), integrates ecological, economic, and human processes, stressing sustainability and system. Governments and scientists prioritize establishing a healthy ecosystem condition, reflecting different socioeconomic, recreational, and commercial benefits, and complying with environmental management rules.

Land use and land cover greatly effect air pollution in Monrovia, Liberia, a city experiencing fast urbanization and industrialization. The shift from natural habitats to urbanized areas, including industrial zones and transportation networks, lowers the natural absorption of pollutants and increases

concentrations of particulate matter and nitrogen dioxide, particularly in locations with extensive impermeable surfaces (Syaban & Appiah-Opoku, 2024). Mitigation strategies include promoting green infrastructure and urban forestry to improve air quality, comprehensive land use planning to minimize industrial and transportation pollution, and leveraging zoning regulations and the Land Rights Law to safeguard ecological areas and support sustainable urban growth.

Transportation infrastructure boosts business productivity and helps small businesses by providing necessary connectivity ((UN-Habitat), 2023). Monrovia, home to over 1.2 million people, hosts about 80% of Liberia's registered businesses, mainly due to its transport infrastructure (Zalakeviciute, Rybarczyk, López-Villada, & Diaz Suarez, 2018). However, only 734 km of Liberia's 9,916 km of roads are paved, with many unpaved roads in poor condition, limiting connectivity and affecting market accessibility (WorldBank, 2017), (Rao & Iimi, 2018).

The growing number of motor vehicles in Monrovia significantly contributes to air pollution, emitting carbon monoxide, hydrocarbons, nitrogen oxides, and other hazardous materials. The city relies on yellow taxis, low-occupancy buses, and a few high-occupancy buses, but 10% of vehicles lack proper identification, often due to poor maintenance, exacerbating pollution issues (Vaishali, Verma, & Das, 2023). Limited vehicles force residents to walk, highlighting the need for better transportation solutions.

Monrovia's high population density and industrial activities lead to significant environmental pollution, affecting air, water, and soil quality. Industrial waste and untreated effluents increase toxic pollutants in water, impacting urban residents' health (Kansuah, 2020), (Bezuidenhout, 2023). Poor waste management exacerbates pollution, with significant challenges due to unclear regulations, inadequate enforcement, and a lack of public awareness, threatening environmental

sustainability (Suresh et al., 2023), (Unep, 2015), (David, John, & Hussain, 2020).

This study aims to comprehensively examine the impact of urbanization on the regional ecology of Monrovia, focusing on the challenges arising from rapid urbanization and developing sustainable development plans. It seeks to assess environmental degradation, including biodiversity loss and habitat deterioration, and analyze the socioeconomic implications of these changes on public health and quality of life. The findings will provide evidence-based insights for policymakers, urban planners, and stakeholders, facilitating sustainable urban development and helping to formulate long-term sustainability policies for Monrovia's ecological health and resilience.

Methods and Materials

Study Area

Monrovia, the capital and largest city of Liberia, is located on the West Coast of Africa between latitudes 6.3°N and longitudes 10.8074°W, covering an area of 194.25 km² on the Cape Mesurado peninsula. Bordered by the Atlantic Ocean and the Mesurado River, which features a significant natural harbor, Monrovia serves as the primary hub for government activity and economic affairs. In 2023, its population reached 1,678,000, a 3.39% as growth rate. As a cultural and commercial center, Monrovia boasts a mix of urban structures, parks, and coastal landscapes, and hosts significant government buildings like the Executive Mansion, the Liberian Legislature, and the Supreme Court. The city's diverse population, including native Liberians, Americo-Liberians, and immigrants, contributes to its rich cultural tapestry.

Data Collection

Data for this study was collected using a comprehensive approach, combining Landsat satellite imagery, OpenStreetMap data, and AQICN air quality data from 2015 to 2023. Advanced spatial analysis techniques were employed to integrate additional geospatial data layers, such as land use and traffic density, to

understand the impact of urbanization on the environment. Daily observations from 2021 to 2024 allowed for the detection of seasonal and long-term trends in air pollution levels as it has been used in the study done by (James, 2024; Wang & Wang, 2024).

Figure 1. The Location of Monrovia as Seen in Liberia Map

Geometric Calculations Using WGS 1984 UTM Zone 29N in ArcGIS

Geometric calculations were essential for quantifying urban areas and mapping their spatial distribution. The Calculate Geometry tool in ArcGIS was used under the WGS 1984 UTM Zone 29N system, ensuring precise measurements. The Shoelace Theorem and Euclidean distance formula were applied for area and length calculations, respectively, facilitating accurate analysis of land use and infrastructure.

The shoelace formula, also known as Gauss's area formula and the surveyor's formula, determines the area of a simple polygon using the Cartesian coordinates of its vertices and is represented by the formula:

$$Area = \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \left(\frac{x_i y_{i+1} - y_i x_{i+1}}{2} \right) \quad (1)$$

This formula is specifically efficient for polygons, where x_i and y_i represent the coordinates of the vertices. The application of this formula within the specified PCS ensures that the computed area remains true to scale, which is vital for tasks requiring precise delineation of land use, zoning, and ecological assessment.

Length Calculation

Length or perimeter measurements were derived using the Euclidean distance formula as it has been used in the study done by (Knudby, Ahmad, & Ilori, 2016):

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Length} &= \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \sqrt{(x_{i+1} - x_i)^2 + (y_{i+1} - y_i)^2} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

This calculation method was crucial for accurately determining the distances along roads, boundaries, and other linear features in a GIS environment. By ensuring that the coordinate system is set to WGS 1984 UTM Zone 29N (Zou et al., 2024), the tool accurately translates these linear measurements into meters, facilitating straightforward application in field surveys and infrastructural developments.

Analytical Correlation and Interpretation

The study involved an analytical assessment correlating processed building data with urbanization and ecological indicators. Techniques like scatter plotting were used to explore relationships between variables such as building density and vegetation coverage. This analysis highlighted potential ecological impacts of urban expansion.

Air Pollution Calculation

Harmonic regression analysis was applied to synthetic datasets representing PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ concentrations.

The regression model used is:

$$\ln(C) = a_0 + a_1t + a_2 \sin(zt) + a_3 \cos(zt) + \epsilon \quad (3)$$

where:

t is the time in day

z is the circular frequency ($2\pi/365.25$)

a_0, a_1, a_2, a_3 are fitting parameters

Calculation of Logistics Growth Model

The logistic growth model employed is represented by the equation Logistics Growth Model (Windarto, Eridani, & Purwati, 2018)

$$y = \frac{A_1 - A_2}{1 + \left(\frac{x}{x_0}\right)^p} + A_2 \quad (4)$$

where:

A_1 = Initial Area (m²)

A_2 = Maximal Area (m²)

X_0 = inflection point

p = Steepness parameter

R^2 = Coefficient of determination

p -value significance evidence

The logistic equation as shown in figure 5 below modeled the growth of building areas over time, and highly applicable in urban planning and development for predicting future building space requirements and ensuring sustainable growth. This robust model enabled stakeholders to make informed, data-driven decisions in various aspects of urban development and resource allocation.

Calculation for the Exponential Growth Model

We used the Exponential Growth Formula (Chen, 2024), for calculation of the population of Monrovia using the,

$$\text{Population} = P_0 \times e^{k \times t} \quad (5)$$

where

P_0 = initial population,

k = growth rate

t = time

Results and Discussions

Urbanization Trends in Monrovia (2015-2023): A LULC Analysis

Between 2015 and 2023, Monrovia saw substantial urbanization with changes in Land Use and Land Cover (LULC). The residential areas (represented by the color blue) had a significant rise in size, expanding from 63.31 to 70.86 million m^2 in 2015 to 2023 respectively. This expansion is a result of urban sprawl, which is driven by the growing population as illustrated in Figure 2 and 3 below. However, this expansion has negative consequences such as habitat loss, soil erosion, and greater demand on infrastructure. The size of commercial zones (red) remained generally constant, with minor variations around 848,859 m^2 .

Figure 2. Spatial LULC pattern of Monrovia (2015-2023)

These areas sustain economic activity but also add to environmental strain. The expansion of industrial regions, represented by the color yellow, indicates progress in both the economic and industrial sectors. Farmland (green) originally declined from 747,953.82 to

740,405.27 m^2 by 2018 due to urban pressures, but rebounded to over 1.08 million m^2 by 2021, demonstrating attempts to reclaim agricultural land for food security and ecological balance. These changes underline the necessity for sustainable planning to balance urban development with the preservation of rural spaces and infrastructure growth.

Figure 3. Land Use Time Trend 2015-2023

Spatial Pattern Urban Expansion on Built-Up Areas (2015-2023)

The spatial pattern depicts a progressive growth in building density and distribution throughout the years 2015, 2018, 2021, and 2023. In 2015, buildings were predominantly concentrated in coastal regions and core metropolitan centers, with sparse dispersion in outlying regions. By 2018, considerable increase in buildings, mainly in the coastal and central districts, with some expansion extending towards the periphery. This trend continues in 2021, with a more significant spread into formerly less developed areas and higher density in core locations. By 2023, there is tremendous development in the number of buildings, with high density in both coastal and central districts and obvious spread into peripheral regions, indicating rapid urbanization, increasing population density, and urban sprawl as shown in Figure 4 below. These changes underline the necessity for efficient urban planning to sustainably manage growth, assuring

infrastructural development and the protection of open spaces.

Figure 4. Spatial Distribution of the Buildings of Monrovia

Urban Growth and Building Expansion in Monrovia (2015-2023)

Between 2015 and 2020, the building area stayed relatively constant at approximately 17 million m², suggesting a gradual increase. 2020 onwards, there has been a clear rise in the size of buildings, as indicated by the logistic curve that demonstrates a turning point around 2021. This suggests that there has been a substantial increase in urban development activities that intensified during after 2020. The curve approaches a value of 2.0x10⁷ (m²), suggesting that the growth in building area has increased. The logistic model accurately reflects the growth pattern of building areas in Monrovia for the given period, as evidenced by the high R² value of 0.99. This suggests that the model is dependable for examining the expansion of cities and can offer significant perspectives for urban planning and policy-making in Monrovia.

A p-value less than 0.01 means that there is a significance against the null hypothesis, suggesting that the model parameters are statistically significant and not due to random chance. This implies a high confidence in the reliability of the logistic model used to fit the building area data.

The data indicates an initial period of gradual growth, followed by a period of strong expansion beginning about 2020, and a possible stabilization beyond 2023. Having a comprehensive grasp of the processes of urbanization is essential for making well-informed decisions about the future development of Monrovia as illustrated in figure 5 at the bottom.

Figure 5. Time Change of Building Area (m²) in Monrovia (2015-2023)

Overall, the data indicates that Monrovia has experienced significant urban growth over the past eight years, with a corresponding impact on its local ecosystem. This highlights the need for sustainable urban planning practices to mitigate the negative environmental effects

Urban Growth: Analyzing Road Network Expansion (2015-2023)

As Monrovia urbanizes, its road network and traffic dynamics have expanded significantly from 2015 to 2023, reflecting the impact of urban growth on the city's ecosystem. The density of residential roads has increased, particularly in central and eastern areas, indicating population growth and urban sprawl. Primary and secondary roads have also expanded, improving connectivity but contributing to higher emissions and noise pollution. This development supports economic activity but poses challenges to environmental sustainability, including increased flooding risks,

and changes in local climates. Spatial distribution maps show a rise in traffic infrastructure, such as parking and fuel stations, spreading from central locations to the outskirts. These shifts, marked by significant increases in road and traffic infrastructure areas, underscores the need for sustainable urban planning to balance development with ecological preservation.

Figure 6. Spatial Distribution of Monrovia Roads Network 2015 – 2023

Figure 7. Traffic Spatial Pattern from 2015 to 2023

The bar graph below Figure 8 illustrates a clear upward trend in the area dedicated to traffic infrastructure (parking and fuel stations) in Monrovia from 2015 to 2023.

Figure 8. Traffic Infrastructure Area of Monrovia 2015-2023

Impact of Urban Expansion on Population

The spatial distribution of population density in Monrovia, highlights the areas of highest and lowest population concentration. The highest population densities, marked in red and orange, are concentrated in the central and western parts of the city, particularly along major transportation routes and urban centers. This corresponds with the linear trend graph of population growth below, which indicates a significant increase in population, the peripheral regions of the city, where the shades are cooler, seem to represent areas with fewer densities of populations; this is taken as natural landscapes are kept or parts of the underdeveloped urban area. This rapid urbanization and population growth have profound impacts on the environment. High population density areas typically experience greater environmental pressures, including increased waste generation, higher levels of air and water pollution, and more substantial demands on natural resources

Figure 9. Population Density of Monrovia

Population Growth Trends and Urbanization in Monrovia (1940-2030)

Figure 10 illustrates Monrovia's population growth from 1940 to 2030, showing both actual data (blue curve) and fitted curves for different periods (red curve for recent 14 years). The recent 14-year period has a growth rate (k) of 0.03577 per year ($p < 0.001$), higher than the long-term rate of 0.03387 per year ($p < 0.001$).

This acceleration in population growth, driven by rural-urban migration, natural expansion, and administrative boundary changes, necessitates adaptive urban planning. The increased growth rate implies higher demand for infrastructure, housing, and services. Urban planners must consider strategies like vertical housing, improved public transportation, and enhanced public spaces. The graph also highlights the impact of the civil conflict from 1989 to 2003, which disrupted population growth and influenced urban recovery. This study underscores the need for strategic planning to manage rapid urbanization in Monrovia.

Figure 10. Population of Monrovia from 2010 to 2030

Current Condition of Ecological Environment and Potential Impact of Urbanization

Weekly variation of PM_{2.5} & PM₁₀

The weekly average and standard deviation values for PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀, displays the concentration ratios of daily to weekly averages generally hover around 1, indicating that daily levels are consistent with the weekly average. For PM_{2.5}, the highest mean concentration ratio is observed on Monday (1.05), suggesting heightened pollution due to increased urban activities early in the week. Conversely, the lowest concentration ratio is recorded on Sunday (0.92), likely reflecting reduced activities from the weekend. Similarly, PM₁₀ levels show the highest concentration ratio on Monday (1.05) and the lowest on Sunday (1.00), highlighting a similar pattern of increased mid-week urban activities and reduced pollution following the weekend as shown in Figure 11 below.

Statistical analysis reveals minor variations between weekdays and weekends, with a t-test comparing the mean PM_{2.5} concentration ratios yielding a p-value of 0.31 and PM₁₀ yielding a p-value of 0.25, indicating no statistically significant difference between these periods. This stability suggests that urban activities contributing to PM levels are relatively consistent throughout the week. However, the persistent presence of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ at these

levels poses a health risk, particularly to vulnerable populations such as children, the elderly, and individuals with pre-existing respiratory conditions.

Figure 11. Concentration Ratio of Daily PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀

Urbanization significantly impacts air quality through various factors, including increased traffic and industrial emissions, ongoing construction activities, and higher population density during weekdays. These factors contribute to elevated PM levels, with mid-week peaks likely due to escalated activities and weekend declines reflecting reduced urban activity. The consistent yet persistent levels of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ underscore the need for effective air quality control measures and strategic urban planning to mitigate the ecological and health impacts of air pollution. Implementing strict pollution control measures and adopting sustainable urbanization practices are essential to address the challenges posed by urban air pollution and protect public health.

Seasonal Variation of PM_{2.5} & PM₁₀

Figure 12. Seasonal Variation of Concentrations Ratio of Monthly to Yearly Average

The study reveals the analysis of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ concentrations from monthly to yearly variations highlights seasonal air quality patterns. During the dry season (December to March), both PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ levels are high due to increased pollution from heating, transportation, and industrial activities. January shows peak concentrations with PM_{2.5} at 1.83 (std dev 0.59) and PM₁₀ at 1.66 (std dev 0.49). In the wet season (April to October), rainfall significantly reduces air pollution. In May, PM_{2.5} drops to 0.56 (std dev 0.25) and PM₁₀ to 0.76 (std dev 0.20), with the lowest levels in September (PM_{2.5} at 0.30, PM₁₀ at 0.35). Concentrations rise again in the dry season starting in October, peaking in December with PM_{2.5} at 1.95 (std dev 0.35) and PM₁₀ at 1.73 (std dev 0.26) due to increased urban activities. Statistical tests show significant differences between wet and dry seasons. The highest PM_{2.5} levels are in January (1.83) and the lowest in September (0.30). Similarly, PM₁₀ peaks in January (1.66) and is lowest in September (0.35). Urbanization, industrial growth, and heating during colder months contribute to these variations (Hussain et al., 2024; Xie et al., 2016). This analysis emphasizes the need for effective air quality management strategies to mitigate air pollution's ecological and health impacts. Stricter pollution control,

sustainable urbanization practices, and enhanced green infrastructure are essential to address urban air pollution and protect public health.

Annual trend analysis of PM_{2.5} & PM₁₀

The investigation of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ concentrations from 2021 to 2024 gives a substantial understanding of the trends and influence of urbanization on air quality.

In 2021, the average PM_{2.5} concentration was 2.76 µg/m³ with a standard deviation of 2.84 µg/m³, and the average PM₁₀ concentration was 5.08 µg/m³ with a standard deviation of 4.22 µg/m³. By 2022, these levels had climbed dramatically, with PM_{2.5} rising to an average of 5.17 µg/m³ and PM₁₀ to 8.36 µg/m³. This increased trend continued in 2023, with PM_{2.5} marginally increasing to 5.33 µg/m³ and PM₁₀ stabilizing at 8.42 µg/m³. The year 2024 witnessed the greatest values, with PM_{2.5} peaking at 7.60 µg/m³ and PM₁₀ at 10.86 µg/m³.

The harmonic regression model employed in the investigation covers both seasonal changes and long-term trends. The model's parameters indicate substantial cyclical patterns in pollutant levels, indicating seasonal effects such as winter heating, which normally raises pollutant concentrations. The positive trend components in the model underline the growing impact of urbanization on air quality. Industrial emissions, vehicle exhaust, construction activities, and increasing population density are key contributors to the rising levels of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀.

The considerable changes throughout the years further indicate the decreasing air quality. The transition from 2021 to 2022 revealed a large increase in both pollutants, indicating a substantial decrease in air quality. While the growth from 2022 to 2023 was milder, it nonetheless indicated a continuation of the upward trend. The steep spike in 2024 emphasizes the rising impact of urbanization and underscores the need for rapid action to address the causes of pollution.

Urbanization greatly impacts air quality through numerous processes. Increased industrial activities release enormous quantities of

particulate matter, contributing to greater PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ levels. The increased number of automobiles in metropolitan areas adds to this burden through exhaust emissions, which are a substantial source of both PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀. Construction operations, which are frequent in quickly urbanizing areas, generate dust and other particles, further boosting PM₁₀ levels. Additionally, higher population density leads to increased energy consumption and waste generation, which add to total pollution levels.

The harmonic regression approach efficiently captures the dynamic behavior of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ concentrations, offering a thorough knowledge of the processes impacting air quality. The seasonal patterns observed by the model underline the necessity of tackling both long-term trends and seasonal spikes in pollution levels. This analysis underlines the essential need for comprehensive air quality management measures that address the main causes of pollution, particularly those related with urbanization, to safeguard public health and promote sustainable urban development.

Figure 13. Measured and Fitted Concentrations of PM_{2.5} (a) and PM₁₀ (b)

Current Conditions of Water Bodies and Potential Impact of Urbanization

Urbanization significantly impacts water bodies through pollution and habitat alteration. The provided image and spatial maps from 2015 to 2023 illustrate these effects clearly. The image

shows an urban area near a water body, highlighting how human settlements lead to increased pollution and environmental degradation due to inadequate waste management and runoff.

The spatial maps show a progressive reduction in rivers, water bodies, and wetlands over time. In 2015, extensive water and wetland areas existed, but by 2018, urban sprawl began encroaching upon these environments. By 2021, further urbanization led to more shrinkage of natural water bodies. The 2023 map shows a significant decline, with fewer natural water bodies and wetlands.

Figure 14. Spatial Distribution of Water Bodies from 2015-2023

This reduction results from urban infrastructure expansion, replacing natural landscapes with impermeable surfaces like buildings and pavements. These surfaces prevent water infiltration, increasing runoff that carries pollutants into nearby water bodies, degrading water quality and impacting ecosystems and human health. The loss of green spaces also reduces natural pollutant absorption, worsening water quality.

Urbanization alters natural water flows, increasing flood risk by disrupting drainage patterns. Reduced groundwater recharge due to impervious surfaces can lead to water scarcity, affecting local water supply and ecosystem health. These changes degrade water quality and

reduce biodiversity, with long-term environmental and human consequences.

In conclusion, the analysis and image highlight urbanization's impact on water bodies. The reduction in natural water bodies and increased pollution underscore the need for sustainable urban planning and effective pollution control. Protecting water bodies requires preserving green spaces, improving waste management, and mitigating impermeable surfaces' impact on water flows.

Spatial Pattern of Forest Cover and Urbanization Impact on Environment

The spatial distribution maps and bar charts of forest cover, parks, and recreational grounds in Monrovia from 2015 to 2023 reveal a concerning trend of diminishing green spaces amidst rapid urbanization. In 2015, forested areas and parks were limited and primarily located on the city's outskirts, with sparse coverage throughout the urban area. By 2018, there was minimal change, indicating a continued lack of significant green space expansion despite urban growth. The situation remained similar in 2021, with slight reductions in forested areas, highlighting the ongoing encroachment of urban development. By 2023, the trend of urban expansion continued, with forest cover and parks remaining sparse and fragmented. This reduction and fragmentation of green spaces have significant ecological implications. The loss of forests and parks diminishes biodiversity, disrupts wildlife habitats, and reduces the availability of natural areas for recreation and ecological services such as air and water purification.

These changes underscore the urgent need for urban planning strategies that prioritize the preservation and expansion of green spaces (Zhang et al., 2024) to mitigate the environmental impacts of urbanization and support a sustainable urban ecosystem (Dhyani, Basu, Santhanam, & Dasgupta, 2022).

Figure 15. Spatial Pattern of Forest Cover

The bar chart illustrates forest cover in Monrovia from 2015 to 2023, revealing a significant decline due to urbanization. In 2015, forest cover was 373,751.6 m², unchanged in 2018. By 2021, it decreased to 150,814.4 m² and further to 149,117.0 m² by 2023, highlighting urban encroachment.

Parks increased slightly from 311,084.8 m² in 2015 to 321,824.5 m² in 2018, then declined to 304,447.8 m² in 2021 and 259,302.9 m² in 2023. Recreational grounds remained consistent around 22,563.2 m², showing minor fluctuations.

The charts emphasize the reduction in forest and park areas, with significant ecological implications such as diminished biodiversity and disrupted habitats. This data underscores the need for urban planning to prioritize preserving and expanding green spaces to mitigate urbanization's environmental impacts and support sustainability.

Figure 16. Area of Forest Cover 2015-2023

Conclusion

The logistic equation as shown in figure 5 below modeled the growth of building areas over time, and highly applicable in urban planning and development for predicting future building

space requirements and ensuring sustainable growth. This robust model enabled stakeholders to make informed, data-driven decisions in various aspects of urban development and resource allocation.

Additionally, inadequate waste management has exacerbated pollution, affecting water and soil quality. From 2015 to 2023, Monrovia's urban expansion resulted in a significant rise in building concentrations, particularly in central and coastal regions, leading to habitat loss and soil erosion. These observations stress the need for effective urban planning strategies that balance development with ecological conservation.

Air quality analysis shows consistent levels of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀, with seasonal fluctuations indicating the influence of urban activities and climate on pollution levels, underscoring the importance of stringent air quality controls. Urbanization has also severely impacted water bodies, causing a decline in rivers, wetlands, and other natural water sources due to the spread of impermeable surfaces and poor waste management. This has degraded water quality and increased flood risks, emphasizing the need for sustainable urban development and green infrastructure.

The reduction in forest cover and green spaces due to urban growth has had serious ecological repercussions, including reduced biodiversity and disrupted wildlife habitats. These findings advocate for urgent urban planning initiatives that prioritize the preservation and expansion of green spaces to maintain ecological balance and sustainability.

Overall, this research provides vital evidence-based insights for policymakers, urban planners, and stakeholders to foster sustainable urban development in Monrovia. Balancing urban growth with environmental conservation is essential to preserving long-term ecological health and resilience.

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Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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